

NUTRIHEALTH AND WELLNESS

PIG STOMACH

This specimen includes the terminal portion of the oesophagus, the stomach and part of the duodenum. The stomach is a hollow organ which modifies its shape and size depending on its content. It has an eccentric major curvature and an opposite minor curvature.

The cardiac region is the place where the oesophagus terminates. The pyloric region is the opposite area which is connected to the duodenum. Between them, the stomach has a fundus, which in pigs has a small and detached sac named diverticulum. Next to the fundus is the body of the stomach, which terminates in pyloric region. This region is progressively narrow until it terminates in the pylorus, a foramen separating the stomach and duodenum.

The lumen of the stomach has a mucosa with folds which can be viewed with the endoscope.

1. Oesophagus. 2. Cardias. 3. Fundus. 4. Diverticulum. 5. Body of stomach. 6. Pyloric region. 7. Pylorus. 8. Duodenum. 9. Major curvature.

PIG JEJUNUM FRAGMENT

The small intestine is the longest part of the digestive system, and the jejunum is the longest part of the small intestine. The fragment you can handle is very flexible and typically curled. These properties facilitate the progress of its content due to the peristaltic movements. It has a mesenteric border, where the vessels (termination of the jejunal arteries and veins) can be seen. The wall of the jejunum is made of 4 layers, including an inner mucosa with villi, and a muscular layer.

1. Jejunum. 2. Mesenterium (mesojejunum). 3. Mesenteric border of jejunum.

PIG COLON FRAGMENT

The large intestine includes several portions. This specimen comes from the descendent colon. Compare the size and shape of the small and large intestine, which are significantly different, as it is also their function.

The colon also has a mesenteric border, related with the vessels (arteries and veins) as well as 4 layers, including the inner mucosa (without villi), and a muscular layer.

1. Colon. 2. Mesenterium (mesocolon). 3. Mesenteric border of colon.

PIG TRANSPARENT SECTION OF KIDNEY

This specimen is very convenient to visualize the two main parts of the kidney. A peripheral cortex and inner medulla. Also, the renal pelvis is present.

Nefrona, which are the functional unit of the kidneys, are distributed in the cortex and medulla. While the glomeruli are found in the cortex the loops of Henle and the distal part of the collector tubules are in the medulla. Urine is collected by the renal calyces and then by the renal pelvis and ureter.

1. Cortex. 2. Medulla (pyramids). 3. Pelvis. 4. Calyces.

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